

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

Grant Agreement No. 101036756

Regulatory watch – 2024

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Summary

This report compiles all the issues of ZeroPM's monthly Regulatory watch for 2024.

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1 Regulatory watch – January 2024

Agreement on the revision of the CLP Regulation aims to accelerate the adoption of harmonised classification and gives priority to group classifications

The European Parliament and the Council adopted the [provisional agreement](#) on the revision of the CLP Regulation on 20 December 2023. To accelerate the adoption of harmonised classifications, the revised Regulation gives the possibility to the Commission to request ECHA and EFSA to prepare a harmonised classification proposal, which previously was only provided to Member States competent authorities and manufacturers, importers and downstream users. In addition, ECHA and EFSA are enabled to provide, on their own initiative, scientific advice to the Commission and Member States on which substances or group of substances should have harmonised classification. As proposed by the European Parliament, the revised Regulation explicitly calls for the prioritisation of groups of substances over individual substances in proposals for harmonised classification and labelling whenever feasible.

The revised Regulation provides a mandate for the Commission to promote at UN level the harmonisation of the criteria for classification and labelling of endocrine disruptors, PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, the adaptation of criteria for alternative approaches, in particular non-animal test methods, and the assessment of the need for new criteria for immunotoxic and neurotoxic substances. New provisions also aim to speed up the integration into CLP of alternative approaches for the classification of substances and mixtures, in particular non-animal test methods, preferably no later than 18 months after non-animal data are included in harmonised criteria at UN level.

Agreement on the Regulation establishing the Industrial Emissions Portal requires the reporting of emissions of PFOA and PFHxS to air, water and soil

The European Parliament and the Council adopted the [provisional agreement](#) on the Industrial Emissions Portal (replacing the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)) on 29 November 2023. The Regulation requires certain industries (installations subject to IED, mining, UWWTPs, aquaculture, shipbuilding) to report their releases of certain pollutants (listed in Annex II) to air, water and soil, when they are above a certain threshold. The addition of PFOA and its salt and PFHxS and its salts to the list of pollutants which have to be reported, with thresholds set at 1kg/year released to air, water and land, has been maintained in the final text of the Regulation. The Regulation will enter into force in 2028.

Agreement on the Industrial Emissions Directive tightens permit conditions for industrial installations but fails to harmonise rules for setting emissions limits

The European Parliament and the Council adopted the [provisional agreement](#) on the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive on 29 November 2023. The main points of the new Directive are summarised below.

Permit conditions

The New Directive requires that permits contain emission limit values for polluting substances listed in Annex II to the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation which are likely to be emitted from the installations. Compared to the previous Directive, the list

of substances concerned is more specific and can be amended more easily. A requirement to assess the need to prevent or reduce the emissions of SVHCs and substances addressed in REACH restrictions; measures to protect drinking water abstraction points; and appropriate requirements for the periodic monitoring of soil, surface and groundwater in relation to relevant hazardous substances likely to be found on site are new elements that should be included in the permit.

Environmental management system (EMS)

The new Directive introduces an obligation for operators to implement an environmental management system, which must contain a chemicals inventory of the hazardous substances present in or emitted from the installation, a risk assessment of the impacts of these substances on human health and the environment, and an assessment of the possibilities to substitute them with safer alternatives.

Setting emission limit values

The proposal from the Commission that competent authorities should set the emission limit values at the lowest end of the relevant BAT-AEL range, which aimed to harmonised the emission limit values across Member States, was not maintained in the final text. Instead, competent authorities should set 'the strictest achievable emission limit values by applying BAT in the installation, considering the entire range of the emission levels associated with the best available techniques (BAT-AELs)'.

Stricter conditions to meet EQS

The general principle that where an environmental quality standard requires stricter conditions than those achievable by the use of the BAT, additional measures shall be included in the permit, is maintained in the final agreement. The requirement for the operator of the installation, when stricter conditions have been included in the permit, to monitor the concentration of relevant pollutants in the receiving environment is removed and replaced by a requirement for the competent authority to assess the impact of the stricter conditions on the concentration of the pollutants concerned in the receiving environment. In addition, 'where the load of pollutants emitted by the installation has a quantifiable or measurable effect on the environment, Member States shall ensure that the concentration of the pollutants concerned in the receiving environment is monitored'. The results of the monitoring should be transmitted to the competent authority.

Transitional periods

The Directive provides for transitional periods for competent authorities and operators to comply with the new provisions of the Directive: 12 years for existing activities and 10 years for new activities.

Agreement on the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) paves the way for performance and information requirements on substances of concern in products

The European Parliament and the Council adopted the [provisional agreement](#) on the new Ecodesign Regulation on 19 December 2023. The Regulation establishes the general framework allowing the Commission to establish ecodesign requirements (performance and information requirements) for products through subsequent regulations specific to

product groups. Performance requirements may be adopted to restrict the use of substances of concern during the manufacturing process of a product and/or the presence of such substances in the final product, primarily if these substances impede the reuse or recycling of the product. Information requirements may be adopted to enable the tracking of all substances of concern throughout the life cycle of products; the required information will be provided either on the product or be accessible through the digital product passport.

The Regulation defines substances of concern as: 1) substances identified as SVHCs under REACH, 2) substances with certain CLP classifications (including CMR 1 & 2; endocrine disruptors 1 & 2; PBT, vPvB; PMT, vPvM) and substances regulated under the POPs Regulation and 3) substances that negatively affects the re-use and recycling of materials in the product in which it is present. The Commission will be tasked to determine, for each product group, which substances fall under this definition before eco-design requirements can be adopted.

The purpose of performance and information requirements related to substances of concern is primarily to increase product circularity and recyclability. The Regulation specifies that performance requirements ‘shall not restrict the presence of substances in products for reasons relating primarily to chemical safety’, which is regulated by the REACH Regulation. It however raises questions as to how this distinction will be made consistently. Information requirements aim to ensure that information on hazardous chemicals present in the product is still accessible at the time the product is reused or recycled. Possible overlaps with reporting requirements under the Waste Framework Directive (SCIP database) for SVHCs will also likely come up as an issue in the adoption of information requirements under the ESPR.

The Regulation establishes a work programme for the adoption of ecodesign criteria, which prioritises product groups. The first programme should focus on iron, steel, aluminium, textiles, furniture, tyres, detergents, paints, lubricants, chemicals, energy related products, ICT products and other electronics.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation amending Regulation (EC) No 440/2008 as regards the test methods, to adapt them to technical progress: **9 January 2024**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals: **4 March 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks and improving cooperation among Union agencies in the area of chemicals: **4 March 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Directive on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks to the European Chemicals Agency: **4 March 2024**

2 Regulatory watch – February 2024

Provisional agreement on the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive includes Extended Producer Responsibility scheme and PFAS monitoring

The European Parliament and the Council reached a provisional agreement on the revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive on 29 January 2024. According to the [Council press release](#), the provisional agreement extends the obligation to set up urban wastewater treatment facilities applying secondary treatment (i.e. the removal of biodegradable organic matter) to agglomerations of 1 000 population equivalent (p.e.) or more by 2035. By 2039 and 2045 respectively, Member states will also have to ensure the application of tertiary and quaternary treatment in larger facilities of 150 000 p.e. and above, and for smaller agglomerations of 10 000 p.e. and above by 2045. The provisional agreement establishes an extended producer responsibility scheme in which producers of pharmaceuticals and cosmetics would contribute a minimum of 80% of the costs of quaternary treatment. The agreement leaves flexibility to Member States on how to allocate the remaining costs. In addition, according to [ENDS Europe](#), the agreement introduces monitoring requirements for chemical pollutants, including PFAS, as well as for microplastics and pathogens.

The text of the provisional agreement is not yet publicly available. Further details on final provisions will be added to the excel sheet when the text is available.

European Parliament's ENVI Committee proposes generic prohibition of PMT/vPvM and prohibition of PFAS in toys

The European Parliament's ENVI Committee provided its [opinion](#) on the proposal for a Toy Safety Regulation on 26 January 2024. The ENVI Committee proposes to extend the list of generic prohibitions in toys – which, in the Commission proposal, covered CMR 1A, 1B or 2, endocrine disruptors category 1 or 2, specific target organ toxicity category 1 (single and repeated exposure) and respiratory sensitizers category 1 – to other groups of substances including: PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, and skin sensitizers category 1. ENVI Committee's amendments further propose to prohibit the use of PFAS and bisphenols in toys, components of toys or micro-structurally distinct parts of toys.

The Parliament's Internal Market and Consumer Protection Committee (IMCO), which is the leading committee on this file, is expected to adopt its consolidated report in February and the plenary vote is planned for March 2024.

Substance evaluation concludes Benzotriazole fulfills PMT / vPvM criteria

On completion of the [substance evaluation for Benzotriazole](#) (BTA, EC No. 202-394-1, CAS RN 95-14-7), which was included in the Community Rolling Action Plan (CoRAP) in 2016, the evaluating Member State (Germany) concluded that BTA fulfills the criteria for classification as PMT, vPvM, and endocrine disruption for the environment category 1. A dossier for harmonised classification will be prepared in 2024. The evaluating Member State also concluded that 'the ED properties for the environment and the PMT/vPvM status on their own could already be sufficient to identify BTA as a substance of very high concern (SVHC) according to REACH Article 57(f)', although it would require an additional assessment of the "equivalent level of concern" to SVHCs.

The evaluating Member State considers that authorisation would be a more appropriate risk management measure than a restriction. An SVHC dossier should be prepared after the dossier for harmonised classification.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Delegated Regulation providing technical specifications for risk management plans on wastewater reuse in agriculture: **8 February 2024**. This Delegated Regulation complements Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse, which requires that the production and supply of reclaimed water is subject to a permit based on a risk management plan. This Delegated Regulation sets out technical specifications for the key elements of these risk management plans.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals: **28 March 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks and improving cooperation among Union agencies in the area of chemicals: **28 March 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Directive on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks to the European Chemicals Agency: **28 March 2024**

3 Regulatory watch – March 2024

REACH Committee adopts PFHxA restriction

Member States adopted on 29 February [a restriction on undecafluorohexanoic acid \(PFHxA\)](#). The restriction bans the placing on the market of clothing, footwear, paper and cardboard used as food contact materials, mixtures for general public and cosmetic products containing 25 parts per billion or more of PFHxA and its salts or 1,000 parts per billion for all PFHxA-related substances two years after the entry into force of the Implementing Regulation (and three years for textiles other than clothing, with exemptions for PPE, medical devices and construction textiles). The restriction also bans the use of firefighting foams with PFHxA for training, testing and public fire services 18 months after the entry into force of the Regulation (except when fire services intervene at Seveso sites) and for civil aviation (including in civilian airports) five years after the entry into force of the Regulation. The draft regulation is subject to a three-month scrutiny by the European Parliament and the Council before it can be formally adopted by the Commission.

Provisional agreement on PPWR introduces a restriction on the placing on the market of food contact packaging containing PFAS

The European Parliament and the Council reached a [provisional agreement on the proposal for a Regulation on packaging and packaging waste](#) (which will replace the current Packaging and packaging waste Directive) on 4 March. The provisional agreement introduces a restriction on the placing on the market of food contact packaging containing PFAS. This restriction was initially proposed by the European Parliament and raised intensive debates across institutions, linked to likely overlaps with the PFAS restriction under REACH, currently under development, which should apply to food contact material and packaging for consumer articles. To avoid overlaps with the REACH restriction, the provisional agreement tasks the Commission to assess the need to amend the restriction under the Packaging and packaging waste Regulation within four years of the date of application of the Regulation.

The agreement is, however, at risk of not being endorsed, for reasons unrelated to the PFAS ban. According to [ENDS Europe](#), the European Commission could formally block the provisional agreement found by the Parliament and Council based on concerns of “unintentional trade impacts” of a provision excluding imported plastic waste from EU recycling targets. A formal Commission objection could only be overcome by a unanimous vote in the Council, which is unlikely to happen.

Provisional agreement on Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive – follow up to last month’s regulatory watch; further details on the agreement (which has now been [published](#)) are available in the excel sheet.

ECHA consults on the draft recommendation for inclusion of Melamine in the Authorisation List

Melamine was included in the Candidate List for authorisation on 17 January 2023, after it was identified as a substance meeting the criteria of Article 57(f) of the REACH Regulation (substance which gives rise to an equivalent level of concern to other

substances meeting SVHC criteria). Based on the large volume melamine manufactured and/or imported into the EU that would fall within the scope of authorization (> 10,000 t/y) and the wide dispersiveness of uses of the substance, ECHA considers that melamine receives priority among the substances on the Candidate List for inclusion in Annex XIV to the REACH Regulation. ECHA proposes to apply standard latest application date (date of inclusion in Annex XIV plus 18, 21 or 24 months) and sunset date (Latest application date + 18 months). Feedback on the [draft recommendation](#) is open until 07/05/2024.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals: **4 April 2024**
- Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks and improving cooperation among Union agencies in the area of chemicals: **3 April 2024**
- Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Directive on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks to the European Chemicals Agency: **3 April 2024**
- Deadline to [provide feedback](#) to the call for evidence aromatic brominated flame retardants: **5 April 2024**
- Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft recommendation for including Melamine in the Authorisation List: **7 May 2024**

4 Regulatory watch – April 2024

CoRAP update lists one suspected PMT/vPvM for substance evaluation in 2024

The [Community rolling action plan \(CoRAP\) update](#) for the years 2024-2026 lists 28 substances suspected of posing a risk to human health or the environment to be evaluated by Member State Competent Authorities under the substance evaluation process of the REACH Regulation. The update from March 2024 added 11 new substances, including 2,4,6-tribromophenol (CAS no. 118-79-6), a suspected PMT/vPvM, which will be evaluated in 2024.

European Parliament votes for prohibition of PMT/vPvM and PFAS in toys

The European Parliament adopted on 13 March its position on the proposal for a regulation on the safety of toys. It includes amendments proposed by the ENVI Committee in January and extends the list of generic prohibitions in toys – which, in the Commission proposal, covers CMR 1A, 1B or 2, endocrine disruptors category 1 or 2, specific target organ toxicity category 1 (single and repeated exposure) and respiratory sensitizers category 1 – to SVHCs, PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, and skin sensitizers category 1. The Parliament further proposes to prohibit the use of PFAS and bisphenols in toys, components of toys or micro-structurally distinct parts of toys.

Commission drops opposition to provisional agreement on Packaging and packaging waste Regulation

Follow up from last month's regulatory watch – The provisional agreement on Packaging and packaging waste Regulation was formally endorsed by the European Parliament on 19 March. Following small revisions made to the agreement, the Commission indicated that they would not oppose the adoption of the text, according to [ENDS Europe](#). The agreement introduces a restriction on the placing on the market of food contact packaging containing PFAS.

Update on the transposition of the Drinking Water Directive

In addition to transposing the Sum of 20 PFAS and Total PFAS parameters from the Drinking Water Directive, the Brussels Capital Region has adopted a parametric value for the Sum of 4 PFAS (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFOS) of 4 ng/l. As in Flanders, which has adopted a similar parametric value in 2023, it is an obligation of means – drinking water distributors must strive to meet this target value by 31 December 2024 – not of results. Three Member States have a binding parameter for the Sum of 4 PFAS (Denmark, Germany and Sweden); the Netherlands, Flanders and Brussels have a recommended or target parametric value. All Member States except Poland have now transposed the new PFAS parameters.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft recommendation for including Melamine in the Authorisation List: **7 May 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for hazard classification of 1,3-diphenylguanidine: **17 May 2024**.

5 Regulatory watch – May 2024

Commission adopts criteria and principles for defining ‘essential uses’ of hazardous chemicals

Announced in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability in 2020, the Communication defining ‘[guiding criteria and principles for the essential use concept in EU legislation dealing with chemicals](#)’ was published by the Commission on 22 April 2024. The communication defines that ‘the use of a most harmful substance is essential for society if that use is necessary for health or safety or is critical for the functioning of society and there are no acceptable alternatives’. These might cover critical uses in a wide range of sectors such as healthcare, energy, transport, water and waste treatment, digital communication, defence, disaster management, environmental protection, scientific research or cultural heritage protection. The definition applies to substances that are CMR 1A or 1B, endocrine disruptors for human health and the environment (category 1), respiratory sensitisers (category 1), toxic to specific organs after repeated exposure (category 1), PBT/vPvB, hazardous to the ozone layer (category 1), and subject to further assessment to PMT/vPvM. The essential use concept will only have legal effect when introduced into specific legislation. The Communication does not specify in which legislation the concept will be or should be introduced or how this assessment will be integrated into decision-making.

European Parliament proposes a different soil monitoring approach and the establishment of a watchlist of soil contaminants in its resolution on the Soil Monitoring Directive

The European Parliament adopted its [resolution](#) on the Soil Monitoring Directive on 10 April 2024. The Parliament proposes a gradual approach to the assessment of soil health (where the Commission proposal classified soils as healthy or unhealthy), which is based on a five-level classification for the ecological status of soils: high, good, moderate, degraded and critically degraded. Only soils with good or high ecological status would be considered healthy. The Parliament proposes a soil monitoring system according to three tiers, each including a range of soil descriptors. Member States have the autonomy to select the most appropriate tier but would have to include at a minimum all soil descriptors from Tier 1. Regarding soil contamination, Tier 1 includes the monitoring of heavy metals in soil, the concentrations of organic contaminants selected by Member States (taking into account substances covered by the POPs Regulation and existing concentration limits in water and air defined by EU legislation), plant protection product candidates for substitution and substances authorised under emergency regime, biocide residues and PFAS (Sum of PFAS or PFAS total).

Based on monitoring carried out by Member States, the Parliament also proposes the establishment of a list of priority substances, followed by a watchlist of soil contaminants, mirroring existing mechanisms for surface and groundwater, to improve data on contaminants when they are insufficient. Regarding contaminated sites, the Parliament specifies that decontamination of sites should always be considered as the first risk management measure. The Parliament does not (no more than the Commission proposal) set a timeline for prioritisation and remediation of contaminated sites. On other aspects of the Directive – sustainable soil management practices, land take – the

Parliament weakens the Commission proposal by removing obligations for Member States and removes provisions on penalties for non-compliance.

European Parliament maintains main provisions on environmental risk assessments of medicinal products in adopted resolution

The European Parliament adopted its [resolution](#) on the pharmaceutical legislative package, consisting of a Directive and a Regulation, on 10 April 2024. The Parliament made only minor amendments to new provisions relating to environmental risk assessments (ERA) of medicinal products, maintaining the proposal from the Commission that the ERA must indicate whether the pharmaceutical product contains PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, or endocrine active agents. The Parliament added a requirement to make the outcome of the ERA, including the data submitted by the marketing authorisation holder, public (with the exception of commercially confidential information). The incompleteness of the ERA or deficiencies in addressing environmental risks are kept as a ground for refusing the marketing authorisation. The Parliament also maintained the provision subjecting to medical prescription medicinal products containing active substances (or any adjuvant or constituent) that are PBT, vPvB, PMT or vPvM.

Key legislative files still open as parliamentary term ends

The last plenary session of the European Parliament on 22-25 April marked the end of the 2019-2024 legislative term. A number of legislative files have however not been concluded during this term. Discussions on the ‘one substance, one assessment’ package (common data platform and cooperation across EU Agencies) have only started in the Environment Committee with an exchange of views with the Commission in March. The work on the file will be carried out in the next legislative term. On a number of files, although the Parliament has adopted its position, the Council has not yet reached a general approach. If the Council adopts its general approach in the meantime, interinstitutional negotiations will take place in the new legislative term (files adopted by the Parliament in plenary normally remain valid). These files include the Soil Monitoring Directive, the pharmaceutical package, the Toy Safety Directive, and the revision of the water legislation (WFD, EQS Directive and Groundwater Directive). On this last file, the European Parliament voted to confirm their position (adopted in September 2023) during the last plenary session, avoiding the need to reopen the file in the next term.

The European Environmental Agency and ECHA publish the EU indicator framework for chemicals

The development of a framework of indicators to monitor the drivers and impacts of chemical pollution and to measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation was announced in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability. The indicator framework was published by the EEA as an [online dashboard](#) on 17 April 2024, accompanied by a [synthesis report](#) written jointly with ECHA. The indicator dashboard is composed of 25 quantitative indicators providing insights into the drivers and impacts of chemical pollution in the EU, complemented by 22 ‘signals’ providing additional insights or indicating trends for specific issues. The indicator framework aims to support the measurement of progress towards the policy objectives of the Chemicals Strategy for

Sustainability, assist EU institutions in monitoring the effectiveness of chemicals legislation and help identify the need for future action.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft recommendation for including Melamine in the Authorisation List: **7 May 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for hazard classification of 1,3-diphenylguanidine: **17 May 2024**.

6 Regulatory watch – June 2024

Council adopts its position on the revision on the Toys Regulation

The Council adopted its [mandate for negotiations](#) with the European Parliament on 15 May. The Council marginally amended the list of hazardous substances prohibited in toys (Part III of Annex II), adding skin sensitizers category 1A to the list of prohibited substances (in agreement with European Parliament's amendments), and restricting the prohibition of endocrine disruptors to substances classified as endocrine disruptors for human health (while the Parliament proposed to cover all endocrine disruptors, for human health and the environment). The Council did not extend the list of substances prohibited further, unlike the Parliament, which had proposed to include PBT, vPvB, PMT, and vPvM. The Council maintained the scope of the generic prohibition limited to substances with a harmonised classification (as in the Commission proposal), when the Parliament had proposed to extend the generic prohibition to all substances meeting the criteria of the hazard classification covered. The Council also introduced a ban on toys that have a biocidal function and a ban on the treatment of toys with biocidal products, as well as restrictions to the use of preservatives in toys. Interinstitutional negotiations on the text will start after the elections; the newly elected Parliament could decide to adopt a new negotiating position at the beginning of its mandate.

Commission seeks feedback on the Safe and sustainable by design framework

The Commission adopted its [assessment framework](#) for 'safe and sustainable by design' (SSbD) chemicals and materials in December 2022. To complement it, the JRC published in May 2024 a [Methodological Guidance](#) clarifying some aspects of the framework, and the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) developed a [toolbox](#). The Commission is seeking feedback from stakeholders who are using the framework in order to support the improvement of assessment methods, models and tools. Feedback can be provided until 30 August 2024 on the [Commission's website](#).

Commission adopts regulation for the gradual review of safener and synergists in plant protection products

On 29 May, the Commission adopted a [Regulation](#) establishing the work programme for the gradual review of the safeners and synergists used in plant protection products. The Regulation sets out the approval procedure and the data requirements for the application for approval. The Commission will publish the list of safeners and synergists known to be used in plant protection products by the end of July, which will become definitive after a consultation period by March 2025. The Commission will adopt the work programme, designating rapporteur Member States for the approval of each product, by December 2025, and manufacturers will have until June 2028 to submit an application. The Regulation should allow safeners and synergists to be reviewed within five years of the adoption of that work programme.

France and Denmark take action on PFAS in consumer products ahead of the EU PFAS restriction

Two Member States are taking action to ban certain PFAS uses before the adoption of the PFAS restriction under REACH, which is currently evaluation by RAC and SEAC.

A [draft legislation](#) in France aims to ban the manufacturing, placing on the market, import and export of cosmetic products, waxes, clothing, shoes and waterproofing agents (with the exception of protective clothing and footwear for professional uses) containing PFAS, and of all textiles containing PFAS (with some exceptions for essential uses) from 2030. The draft legislation has been adopted by the French Parliament and Senate in first reading, but still has to be endorsed by the Parliament in a second reading. The Danish government also [announced](#) in April 2024 the adoption of a national ban on PFAS in clothing, shoes and waterproofing agents applying from 1 July 2026 and until the EU PFAS restriction comes into effect. Denmark had already adopted a national ban on PFAS in paper and cardboard food packaging in 2020, later introduced at EU level in the Packaging and packaging waste Regulation.

The French draft legislation also contains a number of provisions related to PFAS in drinking water, including an obligation for regional health authorities to control a wider list of PFAS in drinking water than required by the transposition of the Drinking water Directive (Sum of 20 PFAS), which will be later determined by implementing act. The draft legislation also requires the government to adopt a national action plan for the gradual reduction of industrial emissions of PFAS in water, with the aim of eliminating these discharges within 5 years of the adoption of the law and to put forward an action plan for financing the decontamination of drinking water within a year of the adoption of the law. The draft law introduces a fee based on PFAS discharges into water payable by certain industrial installations to the water agencies (similar to what already exists in France for other pollutants like phosphorus, nitrites or nitrates). The fee (€100 per 100 grams) will help local authorities clean up their water. As mentioned before, this is still a draft law, which must to be endorsed by the Parliament in a second reading before official enactment, and may be subject to further amendments.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the ‘safe and sustainable by design’ framework: **30 August 2024**.

7 Regulatory watch – July 2024

Council negotiating mandate introduces a groundwater quality standard for the Sum of four PFAS but pushes legal deadlines for compliance to 2039

The Council adopted its [negotiating mandate](#) on the revisions of the Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive and Environmental Quality Standards Directive on 19 June.

Environmental quality standards for surface waters: The Council maintained the Commission's proposal on setting environmental quality standards for the sum of 24 PFAS in surface water, and deleted the EQS for total active substances in pesticides, their relevant metabolites, degradation and reaction products. The Council also delayed the legal deadline for compliance with revised EQS to 2033 and with newly introduced substances (including PFAS, diclofenac or ibuprofen) to December 2039.

Ground water pollutants: As groundwater is the main source for drinking water in many Member States, the Council aligned the groundwater quality standard for the Sum of PFAS with the Drinking Water Directive, which set a parametric value for the Sum of 20 PFAS – the original proposal from the Commission had set a groundwater quality standard for the Sum of 24 PFAS. The Council negotiating mandate however recognised that the Drinking Water Directive parameter for the Sum of PFAS is not in line with the latest scientific developments should be revised according to recent knowledge, including on new parameters such as TFA. In addition, the negotiating mandate introduced a groundwater quality standard for the sum of the four most problematic PFAS (PFOA, PFOS, PFNA, PFHxS), set at 0,0044 µg/l. The Council delayed the legal deadline for compliance with new groundwater quality standards, including for PFAS, to December 2039.

The Council simplified the groundwater quality standard for non-relevant metabolites of pesticides and added an obligation for the Commission to establish a list of known pesticides, indicating if they are relevant or not, and to update it at least every six years. This list should support Member States in selecting the active substances to monitor. Regarding pharmaceuticals, the Council maintained the listing of individual pharmaceutical products, but deleted the groundwater quality standard for the total of pharmaceutical active substances.

Watch lists for surface and groundwater pollutants: The Council maintained the maximum number of substances that can be included in both watch lists (5 for groundwater, 10 for surface water), when the Parliament, in its negotiating position, had removed those caps. The Council also requested the Commission to consider the creation of a joint monitoring facility for samples submitted by the Member States, for the analysis of the substances on the surface and groundwater watch lists and for the substances listed for which quality standards have been defined in the Groundwater Directive and the EQS Directive. A joint monitoring facility is also supported by the European Parliament.

Review of surface and groundwater quality standards: Like the European Parliament, the Council removed the possibility for the Commission to amend the list of priority substances and surface and groundwater quality standards through delegated acts. The review of these lists every six years may lead to a revision through legislative procedure.

Council mandate on soil monitoring provides more flexibility to Member States in soil health monitoring and identification of contaminated sites

The Council adopted its [general approach](#) on the Soil Monitoring Directive on 17 June. The Commission proposal set out an obligation for Member States to set up a monitoring framework for soil health based on soil descriptors and criteria for healthy soil defined at EU or Member State level. The Council introduced an approach to monitoring and assessing soil health consisting of non-binding sustainable target values defined at EU level and operational trigger values, set at member states level. According to the Council, the non-binding sustainable target values ‘reflect the long-term aspirational objective of the Directive’ and describe ‘the ideal situation where the capacity of soils to provide ecosystem services will not decrease and no significant harm will occur to human health or the environment’. On the contrary, Member States must set operational trigger values for each soil descriptor listed in Annex to the Directive and take appropriate measures to restore soil health according to these values. The monitoring framework proposed by the Council provides more flexibility to Member States – compared to the Commission proposal – as all operational criteria for assessing soil health will be defined at national level.

Earlier this year, in April, the European Parliament proposed an assessment of soil health based on a five-level classification for the ecological status of soils (high, good, moderate, degraded and critically degraded) and a fully revamped monitoring framework, including, regarding soil contamination, the monitoring of POPs, PFAS, biocide residues and plant protection products. Positions from legislators are quite far apart before interinstitutional negotiations, which should happen in Q4 2024.

Like the European Parliament, the Council proposed the establishment of a watch list of soil contaminants having a high potential to affect soil health, human health or the environment. This list should be established by the Commission within 18 months of the entry into force of the Directive and should be updated regularly (no specific timeframe proposed). Regarding contaminated sites, the Council called for a ‘risk-based and stepwise approach’ to the identification, investigation and risk assessment of potentially contaminated sites and postpones the deadline for their identification to 10 years after the entry into force of the Directive (instead of 7 years in the Commission proposal).

Germany proposes harmonised classification as PMT and vPvM for TFA

Germany has submitted two dossiers for revising the harmonised classification of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and adopt a new harmonised classification for sodium trifluoroacetate and other inorganic salts of trifluoroacetic acid in June 2024. New proposed hazards include PMT, vPvM and Reprotoxic 1B. ECHA is currently running the accordance check on both dossiers. If the accordance check is successful, ECHA will launch the public consultation.

Update of restriction roadmap plans restriction of 1,4 dioxane in surfactants in 2025

The [Rolling List of \(groups of\) substances](#) for restriction, updating Annex I to the Restriction Roadmap, was updated on 1 July 2024. The list includes the restriction of the manufacture, placing on the market and use of 1,4-dioxane in surfactants, for which the Annex XV restriction report is planned to be submitted in October 2025.

Hungarian presidency program prioritises soil monitoring, water and OSOA files

Hungary took the rotating presidency of the Council on 1 July. In the [presidency programme](#), the Member State commits to ‘make significant progress on legislative proposals on microbeads, soil monitoring, priority substances in surface and groundwater, as well as the One Substance One Assessment (OSOA) package’.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the ‘safe and sustainable by design’ framework: **30 August 2024**.

8 Regulatory watch – August 2024

Von der Leyen’s political guidelines for the next five years propose to simplify REACH and provide clarity on PFAS

Ursula von der Leyen’s [political guidelines for 2024-2029](#), published ahead of the vote in Parliament on 18 July that elected her president of the European Commission for a second term, present her priorities for the next five years, where a shift towards competitiveness and clean industry is visible. The guidelines plan for the publication of a new ‘Clean Industrial Deal’ in the first hundred days of the mandate. The guidelines also propose ‘a new chemicals industry package, aiming to simplify REACH and provide clarity on ‘forever chemicals’ or PFAS’, which may refer to the ongoing PFAS restriction, although no further details are provided in the guidelines.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the ‘safe and sustainable by design’ framework: **30 August 2024**.

9 Regulatory watch – September 2024

ECHA identifies needs for harmonised classification as vPvM for certain cyclodextrins

In its [assessment of regulatory needs on cyclic polysaccharides and their ether and ester derivatives](#) from June 2024, ECHA identified that cyclodextrins are potential vPvM substances. Since there is high release potential to surface waters, soil and ground water due to the use in washing and cleaning products for some of the substances, ECHA proposes to confirm the hazard via harmonised classification (CLH) as vPvM hazard for the substances. The report draws no conclusions regarding possible additional EU regulatory risk management until more clarity is available on how to regulate PMT/vPvM substances.

European Parliament Internal market committee upholds position on Toy Safety Regulation

The new Internal market committee of the European Parliament voted on 5 September to maintain the position of the previous legislature on the Toy Safety Regulation. The interinstitutional negotiations between the Parliament, Council and the European Commission can now start to reach an agreement on the draft act.

Council reduces the scope of the data medicinal products in the common data platform

The Council released its [mandate for negotiations with the Parliament on the Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals](#) from 17 June, which brings few changes to the original proposal from the Commission. The main amendment to the proposal is the reduction of the scope of the data related to medicinal products that can be included in the common data platform. The Council proposes that only data submitted after the regulation's entry into force is available on the platform and only data concerning active substances subject to certain regulatory procedures (listed in Annex I part I to the Regulation), with persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic properties or with a known high level of residues in the environment. The Council included a review clause six years after the entry into force of the Regulation to assess whether additional data on medicinal products should be included in the platform.

No upcoming consultation deadlines!

10 Regulatory watch – October 2024

Call for evidence and workshop on the Commission Roadmap to phase out animal testing in chemical safety assessments

The European Commission is preparing a roadmap that ‘outline milestones and specific actions (legislative and non-legislative) to be implemented in the short to longer term to further reduce and ultimately phase out animal testing under all relevant pieces of chemical legislation (e.g. REACH, Biocidal Product Regulation, Plant Protection Products Regulation and human and veterinary medicines)’. The roadmaps should in particular set out a ‘path to expanding and accelerating the development, validation and implementation of non-animal methods as well as means to facilitate their uptake across legislation’. The Commission has launched a [call for evidence](#) to support the preparation of the roadmap, which is open until **15 October 2024**. The call for evidence invites researchers to send research and data related to non-animal testing methods. To support the roadmap, the Commission also holds a series of workshops – the second one will be held in Brussels on 25 October 2024 (hybrid meeting – Albert Borschette Congress Center in Brussels + online. [Registration open until 11 October](#)) and a third one will be held in May 2025.

Restriction on PFHxA and related substances adopted

The [restriction](#) on undecafluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), its salts and PFHxA-related substances, which was approved by the REACH Committee in February 2024, was adopted on 19 September. The restriction, which will start applying from 10 April 2026, bans the placing on the market of clothing and footwear for the general public, paper and cardboard used as food contact materials, mixtures for general public and cosmetic products containing 25 parts per billion or more of PFHxA and its salts or 1,000 parts per billion for all PFHxA-related substances two years after the entry into force of the Implementing Regulation (and three years for textiles other than clothing, with exemptions for PPE, medical devices and construction textiles). The restriction also bans the use of firefighting foams with PFHxA for training, testing and public fire services 18 months after the entry into force of the Regulation (except when fire services intervene at Seveso sites) and for civil aviation (including in civilian airports) five years after the entry into force of the Regulation.

Data needed to clarify PMT/vPvM hazard of alkoxysilyl carbamates

In its [assessment of regulatory needs](#) published on 18 September 2024, ECHA identified that certain alkoxysilyl carbamates were potentially PMT substances based on available data and proposes data generation to clarify the PMT hazard.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) on the Commission Roadmap to phase out animal testing in chemical safety assessments: **15 October 2024**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on the [harmonised classification](#) of choline hydrogen phosphonate (PMT/vPvM listed in hazard classes open for commenting): **25 October 2024**.

11 Regulatory watch – November 2024

Commissioner for environment commits to publish the legislative proposal for the REACH revision in 2025

In her [responses to the European Parliament Committees' questions](#), commissioner-designate for Environment, Jessika Roswall, clarified that the 'chemicals industry package', announced by European Commission president, Ursula Von der Leyen, will include the revision of the REACH Regulation and committed to publish the legislative proposal in 2025. She reiterated that commitment during her [confirmation hearing](#) at the European Parliament on 5 November, stressing that the ongoing impact assessment would be the basis for the proposal, although it may need some adjustments, and that she has 'no intention of delaying the process'. The revision will 'simplify and modernise the regulatory framework', 'review the dual system of authorisations and restrictions, in order to substantially reduce the need for individual authorisations of uses of hazardous substances' and 'improve information requirements in key areas such as endocrine disruptor'. During her hearing, Roswall clarified that according to her 'simplification does not mean deregulation'.

Regarding PFAS, commissioner-designate Roswall indicated that she would 'seek a ban the use of PFAS in consumer uses, such as cosmetics, food contact materials and outdoor clothing' and 'would support the continued use of PFAS in industrial applications, in particular critical ones, under strictly controlled conditions' where 'adequate alternatives in terms of performance and safety are not available'. As no further details were provided during the hearing, it is not entirely clear what this distinction made between PFAS in consumer products and industrial applications concretely means in the context of the PFAS restriction currently examined by ECHA's Committees (i.e. does it refer to specific exemptions for industrial applications as already anticipated in the draft restriction or to something else?). Asked by an MEP about the timeframe for her proposed ban on PFAS in consumer products, Roswall said an exact timeframe was difficult to provide but that she would get the process started as soon as possible, declaration which is also raising questions considering that the restriction process is ongoing.

MEPs have endorsed Jessika Roswall as environment commissioner on 6 November.

Member States call for swift REACH revision and PFAS restriction

Member States discussed the state of play and way forward for the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability at the [Environment Council on 14 October 2024](#). Nearly all Member States called for prioritising the revision of the REACH Regulation for the Commission to present a legislative proposal swiftly, some Member States recalling that other actions under the Chemicals Strategy, notably the CLP revision, will only take their full effect with the REACH revision. Denmark and Sweden stated that the REACH revision should focus on removing hazardous substances from consumer products. Sweden and the Netherlands stressed the need to better take into account the combination effects of chemicals when assessing and setting the conditions of use of chemicals. Both supported the introduction of assessment factors for combination effects. Germany emphasised the

importance of improving and simplifying the authorisation process. Most Member States also supported the implementation of the ‘one substance, one assessment’ principle.

PFAS were mentioned by most Member States, who called for completing the PFAS restriction as soon as possible, with some divergences between Member States. Several stressed the need to preserve uses that do not yet have effective alternatives to minimise impacts on companies. Luxemburg also pushed for drawing a remediation strategy for PFAS pollution. The Netherlands, Austria and Estonia supported the implementation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework, with the Netherlands calling on the Commission to publish a guidance to help companies implement this approach.

Revised CLP Regulation and revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive adopted by Council

The Council adopted the revised CLP Regulation on 14 October and the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive on 16 October 2024. This was the last step in the decision-making procedures. Both acts will be published in the Official Journal of the European Union and will enter into force 20 days later. Following the entry into force of the revised UWWTD, EU Member States will have up to 31 months to adapt their national legislation to the new rules.

ECHA hosts webinar on new hazard classes and guidance

ECHA organises on 21 November a webinar on the hazard classes recently introduced in the CLP Regulation (endocrine disruptors, PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM) and the development of the associated CLP guidance. More information on the upcoming webinar is available on [ECHA's website](#).

No upcoming consultation deadlines!

12 Regulatory watch – December 2024

RAC and SEAC are considering other restriction options than a ban for certain industrial applications of PFAS

ECHA and authorities from Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden have published a [progress update](#) on the ongoing process to restrict PFAS under the REACH Regulation. As of now, the Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) has reached a provisional conclusion on the hazard assessment of PFAS. Given the wide scope of the restriction, the RAC and the Socio-Economic Analysis (SEAC) have taken a sector-based approach to assess the risks and socio-economic impacts of the restriction. The two Committees have so far reached provisional conclusions on five sectors: consumer mixtures and miscellaneous consumer articles, cosmetics, ski wax, metal plating and manufacture of metal products and petroleum and mining. Discussions on at least six more sectors are [planned in 2024 and 2025](#) and new uses have been identified based on consultation inputs (sealing applications, technical textiles, printing applications and other medical applications, such as packaging and excipients for pharmaceuticals).

According to the progress note, following the consultation, Committees are considering whether restriction options other than a ban could achieve the aim to significantly reduce the PFAS emissions throughout their life cycle, in particular for sectors where the socio-economic impacts may be disproportionate. Such options could be setting conditions for the continued manufacture, placing on the market and uses of PFAS until suitable alternatives are available. Sectors where such options are considered are batteries, fuel cells, and electrolyzers, and they could be considered for other sectors, such as medical devices, semiconductors and fluoropolymers.

Commission proposes ban on pesticide active substances degrading into TFA

The Commission has issued a draft [implementing regulation for the non-renewal of the active substance flufenacet](#) under the Plant Protection Products Regulation. Flufenacet is widely used in Europe as active substance in herbicides for cereal crops. In its [scientific opinion](#) published in September 2024, EFSA concluded that the active substance meets the criteria to be identified as an endocrine disruptor and identified very high potential for groundwater contamination by trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). The active substance had been [identified as forming TFA in large quantities by the UBA](#) since 2017 and was considered the most important plant protection product for TFA inputs into the environment in Germany. The implementing regulation will be discussed at the Member States Committee early December and could be adopted at its next meeting, in the first half of 2025.

The Commission has also issued an [implementing regulation for the non-renewal of the active substance flutolanil](#). The active substance is used as fungicide for potato or flower growing. In its [scientific opinion](#) published in June 2023, EFSA identified significant data gaps preventing the finalisation of the risk assessment for consumers, specifically regarding metabolites, including TFA occurrence. Based on its structure (C-CF₃ group) the substance is however suspected to degrade into TFA. In addition, EFSA identified other risks for workers, aquatic invertebrates, mammals and bees, justifying the non-renewal of the active substance.

ECHA updated guidance on applying the CLP Regulation with new hazard classes

ECHA has updated the [guidance on the application of the CLP Regulation criteria](#) with information related to the new hazard classes. The guidance gathers available reliable information to conclude on each property (e.g. P, vP, M, vM), information on the application of a weight of evidence to conclude on classification and labelling, provisions on dealing with multiple studies for the same property, and information on mixture classification. The guidance also contains specific considerations on pesticides and biocides (such as additional test methods or approaches), and other issues like outliers, treatment of values very close to regulatory thresholds, use of (Q)SARs, monitoring data or modelling, and updated information on rulings of the European Court of Justice. During the [webinar](#) presenting the guidance, ECHA recalled that the guidance is an iterative process, and that it could be updated in future years, once additional experience has been built with classification of substances under new hazard classes.

Denmark publishes national PFAS ban in textiles

Denmark has notified the EU about its [national ban on PFAS in textile products and footwear](#) on 27 November. The Danish government had announced in April its intention to propose such a ban, ahead of the EU PFAS restriction. From 1 July 2026 and until the EU PFAS restriction comes into effect, Danish companies will not be allowed to import or sell clothing, footwear and waterproofing agents for clothing and footwear containing PFAS in concentrations greater than 50 mg F/kg. The ban does not apply to other textiles, such as home textiles, and accessories. The ban also specifically exempts personal protective equipment where PFAS content constitutes a safety function, medical devices and reused or recycled items. The Danish government estimates that the temporary national ban will ‘limit emissions of PFAS to the environment in Denmark in the range of 200-300 tonnes per year, which corresponds to approximately 35-50% of the estimated total emissions from the production and marketing of products’.

European Parliament’s rapporteur proposes the inclusion of data on substances in articles and alternatives in common data platform

The ENVI Committee’s rapporteur presented the [draft report](#) on the Commission proposal for a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals on 25 November. The draft report proposes to integrate, as part of the common data platform, a new database containing information on substances in articles and their alternatives, generated or submitted as part of the implementation of EU legislation. The rapporteur also proposes to include data generated under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and made available through the ESPR web portal (containing data included in digital product passports) in the scope of the common data platform to improve data availability on substances in products and alternatives.

Ban on PFOA in firefighting foams delayed until end of 2025

The POP Regulation provides an exemption for the use of PFOA, its salts and PFOA-related compounds in fire-fighting foam for liquid fuel vapour suppression and liquid fuel fire (Class B fires) already installed in systems, which is set to expire on 4 July 2025. Following communications with authorities and stakeholders that many operators have difficulties to respect this deadline, based difficulties in measuring PFOA-related

compounds in the foams and underestimation of the volumes of foams containing PFOA, the Commission proposes to [amend the POPs Regulation](#) to extend the deadline until 3 December 2025, the latest possible date according to the Stockholm Convention.

European Parliament adopted decision to enter trilogues on water legislation

On 4 December, the ENVI Committee voted in favour of entering interinstitutional discussions with the Commission and the Council on the revision of the Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive and Environment Quality Standards Directive, final step of the legislative procedure before the adoption of the text. The Parliament had adopted its position in September 2023 and the Council in June 2024.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft act extending the use of PFOA in firefighting foams until end of 2025 (amendment to POP Regulation): **6 December 2024**

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